

Milestone: M2.2 Collection of existing best-practices and indicators for research software

Lead Participant: TTK

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Date Of Completion: 18/10/2024

Means of Verification

[M2.2 Collection of existing best-practices and indicators for research software](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

- Federica Quaglia (UNIPD)
- Silvio Tosatto (UNIPD)
- Zsuzsanna Dosztanyi (TTK)
- WP2 members and WP3 members

Next action steps

- Update, as a live document, with relevant materials during the next months

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